

Linked Open Datasets on Traditional Livonian Clothing

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This dataset documents traditional garments from the **Livonian Coast** in Northern Kurzeme, Latvia. Unlike our similar the *Latgale* dataset (Pigozne, Antal, and Mester 2025), which is rooted in long-term fieldwork and close inspection of physical artefacts, this collection was constructed through **digital curation workflows**, enabling our team to identify scattered Livonian heritage items across international museum systems, despite limited local infrastructure. This workflow was not automated; we tried various searches on the systems to conceptualize a more thorough, AI supported search that repairs the metadata problems and may bring up further items that are not easily identified by human searches.

The compilation relied on Ieva Pigozne’s domain knowledge in Latvian dress history, complemented by digital search methods and metadata alignment strategies developed by the co-authors. Our primary aim was to **design tools for transnational semantic discovery**, enabling effective metadata reconciliation beyond the borders of Latvia, even if we cannot utilise an RDF annotated description of the artefacts, or if that description is “shallow”, for example, it releases mainly to natural language rdfs:label tabs instead of unambiguous thesaurus or ontological URIs

Compared to our similar efforts in Latgale and Setomaa, the Livonian context presents a unique challenge: a Finno-Ugric moribund-language community situated in a geographically compact area with few surviving institutions. As a result, our emphasis shifted from consulting primary sources toward the **secondary examination** of existing collections—particularly their **digital surrogates** and associated metadata.

Our focus was the cultural region historically known as the *Livonian Coast*, comprising a dozen village-sized settlements, and further named manorial sites, and some already-abandoned other settlements. While our broader project maps the Finno-Ugric cultural sphere, in the case of dress history, by the time primary documentation began in the 19th century, the Livonian population was already **small and largely assimilated** into mainly Latvian, but also local German, and Russian-speaking communities. In tangible or material terms, it is often more accurate to refer to the clothing traditions of *Northern Kurzeme* or historical Courland than using the Livonian ethnonym. People on the Livonian coast dressed

similarly—perhaps identically—regardless of whether they spoke Livonian or Latvian, or if they identified as Livonian.

The primary sources of traditional Livonian clothing are mostly held in three countries – Latvia, Finland, and Estonia. Out of these collections, both Finland and Estonia offer a large collection of digital surrogates, although the Livonian textile collection of the National Museum of Finland is not fully digitised yet. The Latvian sources usually do not offer digital surrogates.

A numerically largest digital collection of traditional Livonian clothing items is housed at the National Museum of Finland. This museum holds original physical objects collected during expeditions by Finnish ethnographers Axel Olai Heikel in 1901–1902 and Emil Nestor Setälä in 1912. The Finnish ethnographers were the first to systematically collect such a large number of traditional clothing samples in Livonian-inhabited territories. Since their expeditions preceded those organised by the Latvian Board of Monuments in the interwar period, it is likely that the majority of surviving Livonian clothing items ended up in Finland.

Another substantial collection of 31 artefacts related to Livonian dress was assembled by the Estonian ethnographer Oskar Loorits during his expeditions to the Livonian Coast in 1924–1925. Finnish and Estonian collections constitute an important source for the study of traditional Livonian dress in the 19th century and its adaptation to more modern fashions at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century. Particularly significant from the perspective of dress history are items necessary for reconstructing a full traditional outfit (key components of traditional women’s dress include shirt, skirt, apron, headwear, bodice or jacket, socks, and shoes).

Neither *finna.fi* (Finland) or *muis.ee* (Estonia) applies a detailed thesaurus for clothing, and they also lack a standardised geographical namespace (for example, Geonames), therefore searches are not straightforward. This is what we referred to as semantically “shallow” descriptions: it is not possible to directly search for “skirts” and Livonian coast in these systems.

Our searches applied:

- Geographical locations after a thorough reconciliation of the place names of the Livonian coast in Estonian, Finnish with the modern Latvian, standardised Livonian, and historical Baltic German names. This gazetteer is also available as a separate data publication: Northern Kurzeme settlements, which aids in geographic provenance reconciliation of heritage materials linked to the Livonian people.
- The names of the ethnographers themselves. Because we know that they were conducting ethnographic expeditions on the Livonian coast, their name triggered relevant results. Moreover, the names of well-known ethnographers were consistently spelled correctly, whereas Livonian place names were often recorded with multiple variants—some of which appear to be mere misspellings.

Multilingual trigger terms (e.g., ‘Liiviläiset’, ‘Livonians’, ‘Kuurinmaa’, ‘Liivinranta’, etc.) were used, although English names had been added to only a small number of place entries. As a result, most of the searches had to be conducted in Finnish or Estonian, respectively.

The garments included in TextileBase (and for the Finno-Ugric context, into the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space) from the collections of the National Museum of Finland and the Estonian National Museum contain the museum’s unique inventory number, as well as a link to the artefact in the open museum catalogues *finna.fi* (Finland) and *muis.ee* (Estonia). Each item is given a label in English that accurately reflects the nature of the artefact in accordance with the AAT (Art & Architecture Thesaurus). A *photograph* and a *description* is also provided, offering an expanded explanation of the artefact’s characteristics. Every added artefact has a defined place in the thesaurus hierarchy, as it is an *instance of*, for example, a *sock*. A *sock* is a subclass of *hosiery*, which in turn is a subclass of *garment*.

Dataset “Traditional Livonian Clothing” comprises 103 Livonian artefacts – garments and costume accessories. These artefacts were identified through searches on *finna.fi* and *muis.ee* using keywords related to their place of origin (e.g. *liiviläiset* [the Livonians] in Finnish and *Liivi rannikul* [Livonian Coast] in Estonian), as well as the names of ethnographers—most notably Axel Olai Heikel and Emil Nestor Setälä—which yielded the most comprehensive results. Each entry was manually reviewed to verify that it included at least one variant of a Livonian place name (further details on the Livonian placenames and their identification are provided in the gazetteer (Antal, Pigozne, and Mester 2025)).

The largest number of artefacts originates from the collection of the **National Museum of Finland**. These items are also the earliest in the dataset, having been collected during the first field expeditions. In total, the National Museum of Finland holds at least 106 artefacts related to Livonian dress. Our dataset includes 65 digitised artefacts from the National Museum of Finland, all of which are accessible via the open catalogue *finna.fi*. These include:

- 2 artefacts collected by Emil Nestor Setälä in 1889
- 43 artefacts collected by Aksel Olai Heikel in 1901–1902
- 19 artefacts collected by Emil Nestor Setälä in 1912
- 1 artefact collected by Lauri Kettunen in 1932

Artefacts related to Livonian dress that have not yet been digitised are not included in our database, although their existence in the National Museum of Finland’s collection has been confirmed by Renāte Blumberga (Blumberga 2006: 175-178, 191-195). These include:

- 11 artefacts collected by Aksel Olai Heikel in 1901–1902
- 30 artefacts collected by Emil Nestor Setälä in 1912

The **Estonian National Museum** holds at least 41 artefacts related to Livonian clothing. All of these have been digitised and are available in the open-access catalogue *muis.ee*. Our dataset includes 38 of these artefacts, excluding three which were considered to be less significant fragments of unspecified garments. The included artefacts are:

- 31 artefacts collected by Oskar Loorits in 1924–1925
- 5 artefacts collected by Ferdinand Linnus in 1928

- 1 artefact collected by Jüri Linnus and Mati Ruljand in 1970
- 1 artefact collected by Lembit Lepp, Jüri Linnus, and Tanel Linnus in 1976

Our dataset *does not yet include* 42 artefacts from the collection of the **Latvian National Museum of History**, collected between 1923 and 1940. Almost all of these remain undigitised. Nine skirts have been partially digitised and are available via the *nmkk.lv* catalogue, but these entries lack some essential metadata, and the use of the accompanying photographs is restricted. The precise number of items of handwear, sashes, ribbons, and other types of accessories from Livonian-inhabited areas held in the collection of the Latvian National Museum of History is unknown.

Dataset DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15668562](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15668562)

Gazetteer: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15668712>

TextileBase UI: <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase>

Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space UI: <https://reprexbase.eu/fu>

- **Graphical view** – Navigate and contribute to detailed entries on musical works, sound recordings, films, garments, and more. Similar to Wikidata, this view supports edits, suggestions, and collaborative enrichment. Explore on Wikibase → <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Item:Q4423>
- **Semantic view** – Export structured data in XML, JSON-LD, Turtle, or N-Triples for reuse in research or digital projects. See an example Turtle file → <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q4423.ttl> or download the XML <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q4423.rdf> or in JSON <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q4423.json>, JSON-LD <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q4423.jsonld> or N-Triples: <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q4423.nt>.
- **Sampo interface** – Search and organize data in a dynamic, tabular format across curated datasets, including materials from the National Museum of Finland, the Estonian National Museum, and collections on Finno-Ugric vocal music and film. Simply click **music** or **films** on the top menu bar of this page. Access via the project page <https://reprex.nl/project/finnougricdataspace/>

The table below shows links to the dataset’s representation in the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space.

title	description	type	current owner	discovery
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men's shirt (SU4920:14)	Traditional Livonian men's festive linen shirt collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sīkrags (Siikrog). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	shirt	National Museum of Finland	Livonian coast
skirt (SU4106:383)	Traditional Livonian women's festive woollen skirt, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Miķeltornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	skirt	National Museum of Finland	Sīkrags

Irbiešu brunči (SU4920:17)	Traditional Livonian women's festive woollen skirt, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sīkrags (Siikrog). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	skirt	National Museum of Finland	Sīkrags
naisten kintaat (SU4106:375ab)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen mittens, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Pīza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	mitten	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis

naisten kintaat (SU4106:373ab)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen mittens, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	mitten	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis
men's mittens (SU4106:371ab)	Traditional Livonian men's woollen mittens, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	mitten	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis

men's mittens (SU4106:376ab)	Traditional Livonian men's woollen mittens, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	mitten	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis
men's mittens (SU4106:374ab)	Traditional Livonian men's woollen mittens, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	mitten	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis

naisten sukat (SU4106:377ab)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen socks, collected by A.O. Heikel on the Livonian coast in 1901 in Miķeltornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	sock	National Museum of Finland	Miķeltornis
men's shirt (SU4106:405)	Livonian men's woollen shirt, collected by A. O. Heikel on the Livonian coast in 1901 in Mazirbe (Ire). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	shirt	National Museum of Finland	Mazirbe

woman's cap (SU4920:1)	Traditional Livonian women's cap collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sikrags (Sikrõg). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Sikrags
woman's cap (SU4920:2)	Traditional Livonian women's cap collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Kurzeme

woman's cap (SU4920:5)	Traditional Livonian women's cap collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sikrags. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Sikrags
bridal headdress (SU4920:6)	Traditional Livonian bridal headdress collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Kurzeme

woman's cap (SU4920:7)	Traditional Livonian women's cap collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Kurzeme
woman's headdress (SU4920:9)	Traditional Livonian women's headdress collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Lielirbe (Iira). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	-

silk kerchief (SU4920:11)	Traditional Livonian silk kerchief collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sikrags. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Sikrags
woollen shawl (SU4920:12)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen festive shawl, usually worn around the shoulders, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sikrags. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	shawl	National Museum of Finland	-

woman's festive shirt (SU4920:15)	Traditional festive linen shirt worn by Livonian women, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sikrags. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	shirt	National Museum of Finland	Sikrags
woman's festive jacket (SU4920:16)	Traditional festive woollen jacket worn by Livonian women, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sikrags (Sikrog). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	main garment	National Museum of Finland	-

apron (SU4920:18)	Traditional Livonian festive apron collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Sikrags. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	apron	National Museum of Finland	Sikrags
woollen sock (SU4920:20)	Traditional woollen socks worn by Livonian men, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Lūžņa (Luuzh). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	sock	National Museum of Finland	Lūžņa

woollen sock (SU4920:21)	Traditional woollen socks worn by Livonian men, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Lūžņa (Luuzh). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	sock	National Museum of Finland	Lūžņa
woollen stockings (SU4920:22)	Traditional woollen stockings worn by Livonian women, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Lūžņa (Luuzh). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	stocking	National Museum of Finland	Lūžņa

woollen gloves (SU4920:23ab)	Traditional Livonian woollen gloves, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Mazirbe (Ire). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	glove	National Museum of Finland	-
woollen gloves (SU4920:24)	Traditional Livonian woollen gloves, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Mazirbe (Ire). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	glove	National Museum of Finland	Mazirbe

woven woollen ribbon (SU4920:26)	Fragment of a traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon featuring a decorative pattern, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1912 in Lielirbe (Iira). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	Lielirbe
brooch (SU2623:2)	Traditional Livonian brass ring-shaped brooch, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1889. Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	brooch	National Museum of Finland	-

mittens (SU2623:4)	Traditional Livonian woollen mittens, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by Emil Nestor Setälä on the Livonian coast in 1889. Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	mitten	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis
coif (SU4106:369)	Traditional Livonian women's cotton coif, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis
coif (SU4106:370)	Traditional Livonian women's cotton coif, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis

mittens (SU4106:372ab)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen mittens, ornamented with decorative patterns, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	mitten	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis
woollen socks (SU4106:378ab)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen socks, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	sock	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis

woollen shawl (SU4106:384)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen shoulder shawl from 1830-1840, collected by A. O. Heikel in Mikeltornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	shawl	National Museum of Finland	-
woollen shawl (SU4106:385)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen shoulder shawl, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Mikeltornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	shawl	National Museum of Finland	-

fabric of a woman's skirt, fragment (SU4106:389)	Fabric of a woman's skirt, fragment. Linen warp, woollen weft. Collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	skirt	National Museum of Finland	-
fabric of a woman's shawl, fragment (SU4106:390)	Fabric of a woman's shawl, fragment. Collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	shawl	National Museum of Finland	-
fabric of a woollen blanket, fragment (SU4106:391)	Fabric of a woollen blanket, fragment. Collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	household textile	National Museum of Finland	Miķeļtornis

woman's cap (SU4106:392)	Traditional Livonian women's cotton cap, collected by A.O. Heikel in 1901 in Sīkrags (Sikrog). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Sīkrags
woman's cap (SU4106:393)	Traditional Livonian women's cotton cap, collected by A.O. Heikel in 1901 in Sīkrags (Sikrog). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Sīkrags
woman's cap (SU4106:394)	Traditional Livonian women's cotton cap, collected by A.O. Heikel in 1901 in Sīkrags (Sikrog). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Sīkrags

woman's cap (SU4106:395)	Traditional Livonian women's cotton cap, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Lielirbe (Iira). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Lielirbe
cap (SU4106:396)	Traditional Livonian women's cotton cap, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Lielirbe (Iira). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Lielirbe
silk kerchief (SU4106:397)	Traditional Livonian silk kerchief collected by A. O. Heikel on the Livonian coast in 1901 in Sikrags (Sikrog). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Sikrags

brooch (SU4106:402)	Traditional Livonian women's ring-shaped brooch used to fasten a shoulder shawl, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Lielirbe (Iira). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	brooch	National Museum of Finland	Lielirbe
man's cap (SU4106:404)	Livonian men's cotton cap from 1850-1859, collected by A. O. Heikel in Lielirbe (Iira). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Lielirbe

maiden's headdress (SU4106:407)	Livonian maiden's head ornament worn for dances, made of a wooden ring and decorated with paper strips, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Lielirbe (Iira). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	headgear	National Museum of Finland	Lielirbe
silver ring (SU4106:409)	Livonian silver ring collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Mazirbe. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	jewelry	National Museum of Finland	Mazirbe
bridal crown (SU4106:410)	Traditional Livonian bridal crown, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Mazirbe. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	bridal crown	National Museum of Finland	Mazirbe

bodice (SU4106:411)	Traditional Livonian women's bodice, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Mazirbe. Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	main garment	National Museum of Finland	Mazirbe
bridal accessory (SU4106:413)	Livonian bridal crown made of artificial flowers, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Kolka (Kuolka). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	bridal crown	National Museum of Finland	Kolka
bridal accessory (SU4106:416)	Silk ribbon, decorated with metal and cotton lace, bridal accessory. Collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Kolka (Kuolka). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	Kolka

bridal accessory (SU4106:417)	Silk ribbon, bridal accessory, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Kolka (Kuolka). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	Kolka
bridal accessory (SU4106:418)	Silk ribbon, bridal accessory, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Kolka (Kuolka). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	Kolka
bridal accessory (SU4106:421)	Bridal accessory (collar), collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Kolka (Kuolka). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	Kolka

bridal accessory (SU4106:422)	Bridal accessory (collar), collected by A. O. Heikel in 1902 in Kolka (Kuolka). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	Kolka
gloves (SU4106:423ab)	Livonian cotton gloves collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Kolka (Kuolka). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	glove	National Museum of Finland	Kolka
bridal crown (ERM B 10:19)	Traditional Livonian bridal crown. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	bridal crown	Estonian National Museum	-

women's cap (ERM B 10:22)	Traditional Livonain women's cap. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	headgear	Estonian National Museum	-
women's headdress (ERM B 10:21)	Livonian women's headdress. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	headgear	Estonian National Museum	-
women's cap (ERM B 10:20)	Traditional Livonian women's cap. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	headgear	Estonian National Museum	-

bridal accessory (ERM B 18:11)	A neck accessory worn by Livonian brides. Collected by Ferdinand Linnus (Leinbock) on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1928. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-
women's headdress (ERM B 8:86)	Traditional Livonian women's headdress. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Košrag (Koštrõg) in 1924. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	headgear	Estonian National Museum	Košrag

festive skirt (ERM B 8:84)	Traditional Livonian women's festive woollen skirt. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in 1924. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	skirt	Estonian National Museum	Ventspils
festive skirt (ERM B 8:85)	Traditional Livonian women's festive woollen skirt. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Košrags (Koštrõg) in 1924. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	skirt	Estonian National Museum	Košrags

fabric of a skirt, fragment (ERM B 18:9)	Fabric from a traditional Livonian women's festive woollen skirt. Collected by Ferdinand Linnus (Leinbock) on the Livonian Coast in Lielirbe (Iira) in 1928. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	skirt	Estonian National Museum	-
textile fragment (ERM B 10:23)	Fragment of a Livonian textile. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	textile fragment	Estonian National Museum	-

cotton kerchief (ERM B 17:12)	Traditional Livonian women's cotton kerchief. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrags (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	headgear	Estonian National Museum	-
handkerchief (ERM B 17:11)	Livonian cotton handkerchief. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrags (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-
women's shirt (ERM B 17:1)	Traditional Livonian women's linen shirt. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrags (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	shirt	Estonian National Museum	-

women's jacket (ERM B 17:3)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen jacket. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	main garment	Estonian National Museum	-
men's jacket (ERM B 17:5)	Traditional Livonian men's woollen jacket with bone buttons. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	main garment	Estonian National Museum	-

woollen stockings (SU4106:379ab)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen stockings, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Mikeltornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	stocking	National Museum of Finland	-
men's vest (ERM B 17:6)	Traditional Livonian men's woollen vest. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	main garment	Estonian National Museum	-
woollen socks (ERM B 17:8/ab)	Traditional Livonian woollen socks. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	sock	Estonian National Museum	-

brooch (ERM B 18:33)	<p>Traditional Livonian metal brooch, typically used to fasten the neck opening of a shirt. Collected by Ferdinand Linnus (Leinbock) on the Livonian Coast in 1928. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.</p>	brooch	Estonian National Museum	-
men's hat (ERM B 18:39)	<p>Traditional festive Livonian men's felted woollen hat made in 1928. Collected by Ferdinand Linnus (Leinbock) on the Livonian Coast in Pitragas (Pitrõg) in 1928. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.</p>	headgear	Estonian National Museum	-

apron (ERM B 10:18)	<p>Traditional festive Livonian women's silk apron. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.</p>	apron	Estonian National Museum	-
woven woollen ribbon (ERM B 10:16)	<p>Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon with decorative patterns. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.</p>	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-

woven sash (ERM B 10:15)	Traditional woven Livonian sash with decorative patterns. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	sash	Estonian National Museum	-
woven sash (ERM B 10:14)	Traditional woven Livonian sash with decorative patterns. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	sash	Estonian National Museum	-

woven sash (ERM B 10:13)	Traditional woven Livonian sash with decorative patterns. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	sash	Estonian National Museum	-
woven woollen ribbon (ERM B 10:12)	Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon with decorative patterns. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-

woven woollen ribbon (ERM B 10:11)	Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon with decorative patterns. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-
woven woollen ribbon (ERM B 10:10)	Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon with decorative patterns. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-

woven woollen ribbon (ERM B 17:7/abc)	Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon with decorative patterns, used as a garter. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-
braided sash (ERM B 17:9/ab)	Traditional braided Livonian woollen sash. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	sash	Estonian National Museum	-

woven woollen ribbon, fragment (ERM B 18:8)	Fragment of a traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon with decorative patterns. Collected by Ferdinand Linnus (Leinbock) on the Livonian Coast in Miķeltornis (Piza) in 1928. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-
woollen shawl (ERM B 8:76)	Traditional Livonian women's woollen festive shawl, usually worn around the shoulders. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1924. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	shawl	Estonian National Museum	-

bast shoes (ERM B 8:73/ab)	Traditional Livonian bast shoes. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Mazirbe (Ire) in 1924. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	shoe	Estonian National Museum	-
women's cap (ERM B 8:75)	Traditional Livonian women's cap. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Vaide (Vaid) in 1924. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	headgear	Estonian National Museum	-
glove (ERM B 10:8/a)	Traditional Livonian woollen glove. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrög) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	glove	Estonian National Museum	-

gloves (ERM B 10:9/ab)	Traditional Livonian woollen gloves. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	glove	Estonian National Museum	-
men's shirt (ERM B 17:2)	Traditional Livonian men's linen shirt. Collected by Oskar Loorits on the Livonian Coast in Pitrag (Pitrõg) in 1925. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	shirt	Estonian National Museum	-
one-piece leather shoes (ERM B 68:50/ab)	Traditional Livonian one-piece leather shoes tied with laces. Collected by Jüri Linnus and Mati Ruljand on the Livonian Coast in 1970. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	shoe	Estonian National Museum	-

woven sash (ERM B 94:21)	Traditional woven Livonian women's sash with decorative patterns. Collected by Lembit Lepp and J&T Linnus on the Livonian Coast in Košrags (Koštrõgi) in 1976. Finno-Ugric Artefact Collection of the Estonian National Museum.	costume accessory	Estonian National Museum	-
woven woollen ribbon (SU4106:380)	Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon featuring a decorative pattern, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeltornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	-

woven woollen ribbon (SU4106:381)	Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon featuring a decorative pattern, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	-
woven woollen ribbon (SU4106:382)	Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon featuring a decorative pattern, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeļtornis (Piza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	-

woven woollen ribbon (SU4106:398)	Traditional Livonian handwoven woollen ribbon featuring a decorative pattern, collected by A. O. Heikel in 1901 in Miķeltornis (Pīza). Antell's Collection, Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland.	costume accessory	National Museum of Finland	-
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